

Nikoloz Sul Khanishvili

Professor,

Faculty of Agricultural Sciences

Yakov Gogebashvili Telavi State University,

Telavi, Georgia

CHARACTERISTICS OF SOIL DISTRIBUTION ON THE TERRITORY OF THE KINDZMARAU LI MICROZONE OF THE KVARELI S MUNICIPALITY

Annotation. The viticulture microzone "Kindzmarauli" is located in eastern Georgia, in Shida Kakheti, in the Kvareli administrative region, on the southern slope of the Caucasus Range, at the coordinates 41°30' north latitude and 45°50' east latitude.

Industrial vineyards are mainly located within 250-550 m above sea level, on the left bank of the Alazni River. The lower part of the territory is occupied by the Alazna Plain, which rises to the north - passes into the foothills and adjoins the foothills of the Caucasus.

Keywords: soil care, Alluvial soil, deluvian deposits, Kindzmarauli

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The territory available for obtaining Kindzmarauli wine material includes part of Shida Kakheti and is present on the left, second terrace of the Alazni River, on the right and left banks of its tributaries: Duruji, Bursi, Chelti, Intsoba, Avanishevi and Shorokhevi. In the north, it separates from the end of the southern slopes of the Caucasus Mountains.

This zone is located within 250-550 m above sea level and includes the administrative territory of Kindzmarauli and Kvareli, the middle and upper part of the villages: Shilda, Yenise li, Sabue, Almaty, Gremi and Shakriani in the western direction, which are located on the second terrace of Alazni.

In the eastern direction of the territory of villages: Fatmasuri, Sanavard, Tsitskanant Seri Kuchatani, Chantliskure, Zinobiani, Akhalsofli, Thilistskaro, Mitidziri, Chikaani and partially Gavazi Shilda and Balgodjiani to the first terrace of Alazni. The total area of this microzone is about 2400 hectares.

Administratively, this zone extends to the administrative divisions of Kvareli, Mitisdziri, Akhalsofli, Chikaani, Kuchatani, Gavazi, Shilda, Enisli, Sabui and Gremi, which are part of the Kvareli Municipality.

The saperavi bud begins to open in mid-April (from 15.IV). Flowering occurs at the end of May, and the beginning of grape ripening is observed in the second half of August (from 20.VIII). Technically, the grapes ripen at the end of September. To get a naturally semi-sweet wine, the grapes must be harvested in mid-October.

Soils – based on repeated studies on the territory of the Kindzmarauli microzone, two types of alluvial soils with nine varieties and two types of deluvial soils with five varieties have been identified.

Soils on the territory of the micro-zone:

1. Alluvial, non-carbonate, large thickness, loamy;
2. Alluvial non-carbonate, large thickness, low-grained, loamy;
3. Alluvial non-carbonate, large thickness, medium-grained, medium and light loamy;
4. Alluvial non-carbonate, large thickness, highly granular, loamy;
5. Alluvial slightly carbonate, large thickness, loamy;
6. Alluvial slightly carbonate, large thickness, slightly grained, loamy;
7. Alluvial slightly carbonate, large thickness, medium-grained, loamy;
8. Alluvial non-carbonate, large thickness, very wet and swampy, clay-loamy;
9. Alluvial slightly carbonate, very wet and swampy, loamy and clayey;
10. Deluvium carbonate-free, large thickness, loamy;
11. Deluvium carbonate-free, large thickness, low-grained, clay;
12. Deluysky slabokarbonatny, large thickness, clay;
13. Deluysky slabokarbonatny, large thickness, weakly grained, loamy and clayey;
14. Deluysky slabokarbonatny, large thickness, very moist, clayey.

The first ten types of alluvial soils mentioned above are represented on the second terrace of Alazani and are mainly characterized by the forms of plain relief, while the 11th, 12th, 13th and 14th types of deluvial soils are represented at the end of the southern slopes of the Caucasus and directly diverge to the southern slopes, which is 400-500 meters

The above-mentioned materials show that the main type of soils spread on the territory of "kindzmatauli" micro-zone of kvareli municipality are "alluvial" and "deluvial" soils with different types. It is also noteworthy that here deluvion, or deluvial precipitation, is formed by the movement of loose material from the slopes oriented south of the Caucasus by melting snow and streams of rainwater or by the action of the force of gravity and sedimentation in relatively settled places (gravitational current, or denudation).

As can be seen from The Legend of the presented map, according to the largest taxonomic unit of the soil classifier, i.e. by the type of soil in the “Kindzmarauli” microzone, alluvial acidic soils – FLUVIZOL – are mainly distributed (on the map N 42). Some researchers refer to alluvial non-carbonate and alluvial weakly carbonate soils by this name (alluvial acidic).

Alluvial soil-FLUVISOL

General characterization. Alluvial soil is characterized by regular flooding and sedimentation of new Alluvion layers on the soil surface. This soil is characterized by a variety of modes, buildings and properties. Their properties are much determined by the nature of the basin where these soils develop.

The total area of alluvial soil in Georgia is 351 400 ha (5%). It is formed throughout the territory of Georgia in various natural zones.

Use. Alluvial soil, as a rule, is characterized by low natural fertility and needs to take appropriate measures, which should be derived from its characteristic features. In wetland alluvial soil, measures should be taken to remove excess water. Particular attention should be paid to the introduction of the correct agrotechnical measures, including the introduction of crop rotation, decent soil cultivation, the use of mineral and organic fertilizers, and the timely conduct of all the necessary work.

The main of these works are:

Soil care and treatment

Autumn and spring plowing of the soil. Minimal soil cultivation. Tending measures - maintenance of soil surface in loose condition (cultivation, milling, mulching).

End of vegetation irrigation one month before the start of harvest, in irrigation-anti-erosion measures on the slopes of medium and large slopes: minimum and zero soil treatment; grass-cord system; soil mulching.

Feeding

The use of organic-mineral fertilizers for cartographic agroregulations.

References

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